

Evolution of vocational teachers' instructional planning in the early years after teacher education

Kim Lê Van

Swiss Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training, Switzerland

Avenue de Longemalle 1

CH 1020 Renens

Kim.levan@sfivet.swiss

Jean-Louis Berger

Swiss Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training, Switzerland

Avenue de Longemalle 1

CH 1020 Renens

jean-louis.berger@sfivet.swiss

Instructional planning plays a major role in the quality of teaching and, by extension, in the quality of learning. Instructional planning, defined by Sardo-Brown (1996) as “the instructional decisions made prior to the execution of plans during teaching,” (p. 519) is one of the central competences that teachers develop during their formal preparation. Moreover, teachers believe that instructional planning was is the most important competence they learned during formal preparation (Mutton, Hagger, & Burn, 2011). Thus changing teachers' beliefs and practices about planning is considered a critical indicator of the success of teacher education¹. Therefore, it is very important to understand how teachers develop these beliefs and practices during their teacher education Instructional planning has been the subject of research from the 1970s (Clark & Peterson, 1986; Yinger, 1979; Zahorik, 1975) to the present

¹ « Teacher education » and « formal preparation » are considered, in this paper, as synonymous.

(e.g., Brodhäcker, 2014). Despite the extensive literature on instructional planning, more research is needed on how teachers' instructional planning change over time, toward various practices and considerations about planning in order to improve process. Furthermore, since instructional planning evolves once teachers have completed their teacher education, the study of planning is needed especially during the early years of in-service experiences (Mutton et al., 2011).

One obvious aim of teacher education is to trigger positive teacher professional development, which includes encouraging teachers and future teachers to develop instructional planning skills. This development depends on a combination of factors, such as enriching teachers' general pedagogical knowledge (Mutton et al., 2011; Wideen, Mayer-Smith, Moon, 1998), changing their beliefs about teaching (Fuchs, Fuchs, & Phillips, 1994), and increasing their self-efficacy (Allinder, 1994). Research has shown that teachers' instructional planning is grounded in a mix of elements, which includes teacher education, teaching experience, and personal life experience (Richardson & Placier, 2001).

Theoretical framework

Recent studies reveal that teacher education has a large impact on novice teachers' instructional planning (Baer et al., 2011; Blömeke et al., 2008; Jones & Vesilind, 1996; Mutton et al., 2011). Based on a study of teacher education in Germany, South Korea, Taiwan, and the U.S., Blömeke et al. (2008) suggested that teacher education had strong effects not only on the development of knowledge of instructional planning but also on the criteria used by novice teachers to evaluate a lesson plan. In other words, thanks to formal preparation, teachers were more knowledgeable about how to plan lessons, and they used a different and a wider knowledge as a basis for planning. Our own study of vocational teachers in Switzerland revealed that after a single year of teacher education, teachers placed more emphasis on students' prior knowledge and teaching methods, and less emphasis on the

material and tasks. A previous study of the perceptions of newly qualified teachers in the U.K. corroborated these findings (Mutton et al., 2011).

In our opinion, most of the aforementioned literature suffers from two limitations. The first is that the time-span was generally limited to the teacher education period, neglecting the first years after preparation, although this is a significant period of professional development. The second is that the studies focused mostly on changes that occurred in instructional planning practices and less on the processes of change. The role of teacher education in changes in beliefs and practices cannot be fully understood unless it is evaluated in combination with the impacts of other factors, such as teaching experience,² mentoring, preferences related to teaching styles, or prior experiences as a student. Accordingly, the present study investigated the following research questions:

- a) What changes in instructional planning practices did teachers report after commencing teaching?
- b) What sources did they attribute these changes to and how did they describe the processes of change?

Method

The present study is based on qualitative data from a mixed-method study of full-time vocational teachers, in the French-speaking part of Switzerland, a few years after they had completed their teacher education. Included were 14 semi-structured interviews with six women and eight men, with a mean teaching experience of 9.5 years (Range = 5–26 years), teaching in both practical and theoretical subjects, all of whom had completed their teacher education 1–5 years before the interviews. This included prior experience (in various professions) before formal preparation³ that the interviewees considered as teaching. They

² In Switzerland, vocational teachers start teaching in vocational schools some years before entering teacher education, and they continue teaching while undertaking the teacher education program.

³ Some of the interviewees taught while working in another area unrelated to teaching; others had other form of teacher training.

undertook the formal preparation simultaneously with a teaching job in a vocational school that included theoretical courses, as well as teacher-educator visits in the classroom.

Regarding instructional planning, formal preparation aims at developing various competencies, such as being able to elaborate teaching sequences in accordance with the lesson plan, structure a course, and select appropriate learning and planning methods.

Pseudonyms were given to all the participants to ensure confidentiality. Table 1 provides a summary of the participants' characteristics.

The interview lasted from 45 to 90 minutes. The protocol included 20 questions focused on four topics: (1) teachers' prior teaching experience, (2) the general evolution of teaching practices, (3) the evolution of teaching practices in classroom management, and (4) the evolution of their instructional planning beliefs and practices. The motivation to become a vocational teacher, in addition to their self-efficacy and perceptions of teacher education, was also explored.

The poster will focus specifically on the evolution of teaching practices in instructional planning. This part of the interview included questions related to past and present planning practices, as well as questions about the role of formal preparation, classroom experience, or other elements in the evolution of practice. The interviews were audio recorded and fully transcribed verbatim.

Once collected, the transcriptions were imported in the coding software NVivo 10 (QSR International, 2012). Data analysis followed an iterative process of content analysis and coding development,⁴ drawing on the literature on the impact of teacher education on teachers' evolution of teaching practices. Instructional planning was divided into six categories, each of which included several codes (Saldaña 2013): (1) considerations that brought about changes in instructional planning, (2) instructional planning practices, (3)

⁴ All the interviews were coded by the first author based on a coding system developed by both authors.

sources of evolution in instructional planning, (4) consequences of applying a specific practice, (5) perception of teacher education, and (6) self-perception as a planner. Each code was enriched with the following subcodes: “related to present/past practice” and “helpful/not helpful in the evolution of planning practice.” Table 2 presents details on the coding categories and related codes.

Results

The interviews revealed that “a good planner” was considered a teacher able to manage time, who was flexible, considered student’s profiles, and had a comprehensive planning structure in place (concerned with objectives, lesson plans, and methods). The results revealed that a basis for changing practices is due to a teachers’ dissatisfaction with the way in which they had planned instruction in their first years as a teacher prior to formal preparation. The teachers reported that their instructional planning practices evolved with some favoring greater flexibility and others preferring a more structured approach, as illustrated by one of the interviewees, Philipp:

“I used to spend a lot of time on individual chapters until I felt that objectives of that chapter had been reached and only then proceed to an evaluation. If I have had a program, I would have said to students, since the beginning, on the 8th of March they will have an evaluation.” (Philipp)

The analysis of the interviews also revealed an important change in long-term planning. After the formal preparation, the teachers reported increased consideration of long-term planning to help them to reach long-term objectives. They then routinely implemented these long-term objectives into their planning:

“In the beginning, I paid no attention at all to objectives. I based [my plan structure] only on the official course materials. [...] Now I know the most covered themes in exams. [...] So I can be more effective.” (Thomas)

The initial lack of satisfaction with planning practices and the reported improvements in these practices enhanced the teachers' self-efficacy beliefs.

Generally, the most frequent changes in planning practices reported were those related to didactics and teacher-student relationships. With regard to didactics, the interviewees reported finding more suitable ways to attribute time to tasks, to take some distance from official study plans or to adopt a more structured approach to planning). The teacher-student relationship also appeared to be a significant motivator of instructional planning changes, with the teachers including class-specific features, such as the student's needs, level of knowledge, or rhythm of learning, in planning.

The sources of the changes were divided into three dimensions: teacher education, "significant others," and personal factors. Teacher education was one of the strongest sources of evolution in planning practices: the impact of the courses taken, teacher educators, and exchanges with other students during the formal preparation.

"Significant others" also played a major role in the evolution of planning practices. Colleagues, trainers, and interactions with peers encountered during the formal preparation were mentioned as triggering an evolution in instructional planning practices.

Personal factors also had a major impact on planning practices. The interviews revealed recurrent and spontaneous answers about sources of changes including the influence of fieldwork and experience, a willing of improved relationship with students, a look for personal comfort and improved time-management.

Although the extent (years) of prior teaching experience of the interviewees differed greatly, the number of years' experience did not seem to have a strong impact on changer in planning practices. The same applied to subject matter, which did not seem to be a source of change in planning practice.

Discussion

Changes in instructional planning were found to be not only due to formal preparation, but also to encounters with “significant others”, and to personal factors, which corroborates the research by Richardson and Placier (2001). This study shows that teachers learn about planning both during and after completing their formal education (Mutton et al.,2011). The intensive conduct and extensive interview coding revealed that flexibility, time management, structure (specificity, clarity, and organization of lesson plans based on learning objectives and congruent teaching methods), and consideration of students’ profile (abilities, interests, preferred learning style) were the most valued features of “good planning.” In the present study, the majority of the teachers referred to these ideals when discussing their current instructional planning practices, increasing their perception of self-efficacy (Allinder,1994). They emphasized the need for flexibility toward contingences and detailed, structured planning. Such practices are essential in the implementation of long-term planning objectives. They appeared to progressively gain centrality in teachers’ instructional planning over time after they have completed their formal preparation. The sources of changes in planning practices were more strongly related to contact with other professionals (e.g., colleagues, mentors, trainers, and teacher educators) than to official requirements. Prior teaching experience and the subject matter did not appear to act as sources of changes in planning practices. At least, teachers did not spontaneously refer to these elements in their discourse. This may have occurred because questions directly addressing prior teaching experience and the subject matter would have been necessary to capture their roles (if any) in instructional planning change. In conclusion, in the optimization of instructional planning, the teachers appeared to search for a balance between competencies that the students must develop and personal factors.

Significance of the study

This study shed light not only on how the teachers changed their instructional planning practices but also, and more importantly, on the combination of factors that triggered these changes and the processes of change. The qualitative methodology makes it difficult to generalize the results. Nevertheless, this in-depth investigation allowed us to uncover the complex nature of the changes that occurred. The results can be used to inform teacher educators of the impact not only of formal preparation, but also of encounters with “significant others”, and personal factors on instructional planning practices.

REFERENCES

- Allinder, R. M. (1994). The relationship between efficacy and the instructional practices of special education teachers and consultants. *Teacher Education and Special Education, 17*, 86–95. doi: 10.1177/088840649401700203
- Baer, M., Kocher, M., Wyss, C., Guldemann, T., Larcher, S., & Dörr, G. (2011). Lehrerbildung und Praxiserfahrung im ersten Berufsjahr und ihre Wirkung auf die Unterrichtskompetenzen von Studierenden und jungen Lehrpersonen im Berufseinstieg [Teacher training and practical experiences in the first year of work and their effects on the teaching competencies of students and teachers at the start of their career]. *Zeitschrift für Erziehungswissenschaften, 14*, 85–117. doi: 10.1007/s11618-011-0168-5
- Blömeke, S., Paine, L., Houang, R., Hsieh, F., Schmidt, W., Han, S., Santillan, M., Schwille, J. (2008). Future teachers' competence to plan a lesson: first results of a six-country study on the efficiency of teacher education. *ZDM Mathematics Education, 40*, 749–762. doi: 10.1007/s11858-008-0123-y
- Brodhacker. (2014). *Unterrichtsplanningkompetenzen im Praktikum. Einflussfaktoren auf die Veränderung der wahrgenommenen Kompetenz von Studierenden [Teachers' instructional planning competences in internship. The factors influencing change in students' perceived competences]*. Münster, Germany: Waxmann.
- Clark, C. & Peterson, P. (1986). Teachers' thought processes. In M. Wittrock (Ed.), *Handbook of research on teaching* (3rd ed., pp. 255–296). New York: Macmillan.
- Fuchs, L. S., Fuchs, D., & Phillips, N. (1994). The relation between teachers' beliefs about the importance of good students work habits, teacher planning, and student achievement. *The Elementary School Journal, 94*(3), 331–345.
- Lê Van, K. & Berger, J.-L. (2016). Evolution of vocational teachers' instructional planning in the early years after teacher education. *AERA Conference Proceedings*.

- Jones, M. G. & Vesilind, E. (1996). Putting practice into theory: Changes in the organization of preservice teachers' pedagogical knowledge. *American Educational Research Journal*, 33(1), 91–117. doi: 10.3102/00028312033001091
- Mutton, T., Hagger, H., & Burn, K. (2011). Learning to plan, planning to learn: the developing expertise of beginning teachers. *Teachers and Teaching*, 17(4), 399–416. doi: 10.1080/13540602.2011.580516
- QSR International (2012). NVivo qualitative data analysis software Version 10.
- Richardson, V. & P. Placier (2001). Teacher change. In V. Richardson (Ed.), *Handbook of research on teaching* (4th ed., pp. 905–947). Washington, DC: American Educational Research Association.
- Saldaña, J. (2013). *The coding manual for qualitative researchers*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Sardo-Brown, D. (1996). A longitudinal study of novice secondary teachers' planning: Year two. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 12(5), 519–530. doi: 10.1080/0260747900160104
- Wideen, M., Mayer-Smith, J., Moon, B. (1998). A critical analysis of the research on learning to teach: making the case for an ecological perspective on inquiry. *Review of Educational Research*, 68(2), 130–178. doi: 10.3102/00346543068002130
- Yinger, R. (1979). Routines in teacher planning. *Theory into Practice*, 18(3), 163–169. doi: 10.1080/00405847909542827
- Zahorik, J. A. (1975). Teachers' planning models. *Educational Leadership*, 33, 134–139.
- Lê Van, K. & Berger, J.-L. (2016). Evolution of vocational teachers' instructional planning in the early years after teacher education. *AERA Conference Proceedings*.

APPENDIX

Table 1. *Description of the Participants*

Pseudo	Sex	Age	Subject taught	Teaching experience	Yrs. after graduation	Prior occupation(s)
Alice	F	32	General knowledge	6	1	Ski resort establishment manager Forensic psychologist for the child welfare system
John	M	39	Landscape technology	10	1	Landscape architect Environmental education and training
Thomas	M	31	Economy Computer science	5	2	Bank employee Audit
Lucy	F	35	Paramedical field	7	4	Medical secretary Paramedic
Philipp	M	34	Mathematics Physics	6	3	
Arthur	M	34	Automotive technology	11	3	Sale and technology workshop
Marie	F	49	Technical subjects for social care workers	6	1	Social worker Substitute in day care
Jimmy	M	47	Automotive technology	9	3	Garage employee Garage employer
Elsa	F	38	Pharmacy	7	1	Pharmacist
Jack	M	44	General knowledge Mathematics	17	3	Primary school teacher Secondary school teacher Teacher for adults (open university)
Danny	M	40	Anatomy Physiopathology Professional skills	9	4	Paramedic
Aurora	F	40	General knowledge	8	5	Art gallery attendant School support, substitute teacher
Anna	F	36	Project supervision Art history Photography history Contemporary arts	6	1	Gallery owner Bookseller
Eric	M	48	General knowledge	26	2	Quartermaster sergeant Editor Secondary school teacher Athletics coach

Table 2. *Coding Categories*

Category	Definition	Codes
<i>Considerations impacting on instructional planning</i>	The elements teachers take into consideration when planning instruction. This includes didactical aspects, relationship with students, contingencies management, adequacy to institutional programs, specificities of subject matter, and prior experience as a student.	Didactical Relationship to students Institutional prescriptions Contingencies management Personal factors Homogeneity amongst colleagues' teaching program Skill reference data Specificities to subject Life past experience as a student
<i>Instructional planning practices</i>	The form of instructional planning embraced. This includes setting objectives, designing activities, the degree of planning's details, the type of plan (written, mental), and the degree of flexibility in the plan.	Objectives Activities Level of detail in lesson plan Type of lesson plan Written/mental lesson plan Flexibility
<i>Sources of instructional planning evolution</i>	The factors at the origin of the evolution. This includes formal preparation, significant other (e.g., mentors), and personal factors.	Teacher education Significant other Personal factors Requirements
<i>Consequences of applying a specific practice</i>	The impact the evolution had on classroom management, personal life, and student's learning.	Classroom management Personal life Student learning
<i>Perceptions of teacher education</i>	The way teachers see the quality or features of teacher education.	Perception of teacher education
<i>Self-perceptions as a planner</i>	Self-efficacy beliefs, perceived value and cost of instructional planning	Perception of self-efficacy Perceived cost Task value